

Continuity Equation Versus Free Particle Flow/Flux Quantum Equations Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 27, 2022

In the literature (e.g. (1)) the Schrodinger equation is sometimes derived using classical fluid equations which follow from Boltzmann's transport equations. In particular a continuity equation and a conservation of momentum equation involving the potential $dV(x)/dx$ are used. We have argued in Part I that the continuity equation leads to $0+0=0$ for a free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ because density is 1. Furthermore a bound quantum state also leads to $0+0=0$ partly because d/dt partial density(x) =0.

Following the analysis of (1) for which a new field $S(x,t)$ is introduced through $u(x,t)$ =velocity field = d/dx partial $S(x,t)$ one may see that the solution $S(x,t)= f(t)$ for any function f yields $u(x,t)=0$ for a bound state. In fact, for a bound state, the continuity equation contributes nothing to the derivation of the Schrodinger equation except for the result density(x) (no t present) which is known already. The Schrodinger equation for the bound state follows completely from the fluid transport equation containing dV/dx . For this to occur, however, one must use $S(x,t)=-Et$. It seems, however, that for a bound state with $u(x,t)$ the natural approach is to have $S(x,t) =0$. Setting $S(x,t)= -Et$ is equivalent to having $\exp(-iEt)$ appear in the wavefunction and we argue in this note that this is an independent assumption which does not follow from fluid mechanics.

In particular, we link $-Et$ for the bound state to $A(x,t)$ =classical action = $-Et+px$. For a bound state there is an average energy value, but overall p average is 0. For the free particle quantum system we argued that two flow flux equations d/dx partial $A = p$ ((1a)) and d/dt partial $A = -E$ ((1b)) govern the system. These may be written separately as eigenvalue equations yielding: id/dt partial $\exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ ((2a)) and $-id/dx$ partial $\exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ ((2b)).

We show that $\exp(-iEt)$ for the bound state is a built-in assumption needed to make the fluid mechanical equation approach to the Schrodinger equation work. As a result, this assumption $id/dt \exp(iA)=E \exp(iA)$ needs to be presented together with the two fluid equations, otherwise one does not derive the Schrodinger equation. In fact, one may use ((1a)) and ((1b)), the two flux/flow equations we propose for a free particle and create a momentum distribution $P(x/p) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x)$ =wavefunction = $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Using conservation of energy at each x point: $[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)] / W + V(x) = E$ leads to the Schrodinger equation without the use of fluid equations.

Flow/Flux Equations

In previous notes we have argued that two flow/flux equations may be used to describe the classical action, free particle quantum mechanics (relativistic/nonrelativistic) and classical waves e.g. sound and light. In addition, we argue that the form of special relativity also follows from the solution. The equations are:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b))$$

A solution is $A= -Et+px$ which is Lorentz invariant. This solution is equivalent to the classical free particle relativistic action: $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ with $c=1$. Classical waves emerge if one uses

$dA=0=-Edt + pdx$. If one considers a particle with rest mass then $dA=0 = dE/dv (-t) + dp/dv (x)$ with $x/t=v$; this leads to a differential equation in E with $p=Ev$ which leads to the form of special relativity. (We have shown in a previous note that one may obtain the form of special relativity even without the assumption of $p=Ev$.) Finally free particle quantum mechanics follows if one writes ((1a)) and ((1b)) as eigenvalue equations:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2a)) \text{ and } -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((2b))$$

A free particle solution is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. To obtain the Schrodinger equation, one may consider a conditional probability for a bound state:

$$P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

Using conservation of average energy at each x :

$$[\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \exp(ipx)] / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

leads to the Schrodinger equation. One may use $E_n W = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} W(x,t)$ with $W(t) = \exp(-iE_n t)$ for a bound state.

Schrodinger Equation from Classical Fluid Equations

There are a number of derivations of the Schrodinger equation from the conservation of mass and the conservation of momentum fluid equations which follow from the Boltzmann transport equation. In this note we consider the approach of (1). The two fluid equations are:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } d(x,t) + \text{grad dot } d(x,t)u(x,t) = 0 \quad ((5a))$$

continuity equation $d(x,t)=\text{density}$ $u(x,t)=\text{velocity field (vector)}$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } (m d(x,t) u_i(x,t)) + \frac{d}{dx_j} d(x,t) s_{ij} + d(x,t) \frac{dV}{dx_i} = 0 \quad ((5b))$$

$$\text{Where } s_{ij} = m \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$$

The author of (1) defines $e = \ln(d(x,t))$ and makes a key assumption:

$$u(x,t) = 1/m \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } S(x,t) \quad ((6))$$

In other words a new function $S(x,t)$ is introduced. The “catch” is that for $u(x,t)=0$, as in a bound state case, one may have

$$S(x,t) = f(t) \quad \text{where } f(t) \text{ is any function} \quad ((7))$$

The issue is that only one special function, namely:

$$f(t) = -Et \quad ((8))$$

“works” for the bound state case. In fact, for a bound state for which $d(x,t) = d(x)$ a priori, the continuity equation ((5a)) contributes nothing other than $d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t) = 0$ which is already known.

For a bound state, ((5b)) the momentum classical fluid equation becomes {Equation 35 in (1)}:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } S - qq/2m d/dx de/dx - qq/8m de/dx de/dx + 1/2m (dS/dx) dS/dx + V(x) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

Here $e = \ln(d(x,t))$, q is a constant and $V(x)$ the potential. The steps necessary to obtain ((9)) are given in (1) and are not repeated here. The main point is that for a bound state:

$$u(x,t) = 1/m dS(x,t)/dx = 0 \quad \text{but what does one do with: } d/dt \text{ partial } S(x,t)?$$

In principle: $S(x,t) = f(t)$ where $f(t)$ is any function, but only

$$f(t) = -Et \quad ((10))$$

allows ((9)) to become the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus there is an extra assumption which must be used together with the classical fluid equations, namely:

$$u(x,t) = -Et \quad \text{for a bound state}$$

We argue that one needs a principle to deal with this issue and suggest the use of the two flux/flow equations: $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$. These written as eigenvalue equations lead to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Writing a momentum distribution of free particles $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$ where $W = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ together with conservation of energy at each x also yields the Schrodinger equation without any need for classical fluid equations. It may be noted that for the bound state there is an average E (energy), but no overall momentum so only $\exp(-iEt)$ appears for the overall solution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, there are a number of derivations in the literature of the Schrodinger equation from two classical fluid equations which follow from Boltzmann’s transport equation. The first is the continuity equation and the second an equation related to conservation of momentum. We consider a derivation given in (1) and note that the velocity field of classical fluid dynamics $u(x,t)$ is written as $d/dx \text{ partial } S(x,t)$. In other words a new field $S(x,t)$ is introduced. For a bound state this leads to an ambiguity as $S(x,t) = f(t)$ is a solution for $u(x,t) = 0$ for any function f . Furthermore for a bound state, $u(x,t) = 0$ and so one would naturally assume $S(x,t) = 0$ or a constant.

For the bound state the continuity equation yields $d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t) = 0$ which is already known, so it is not really needed. The conservation of momentum equation must yield the Schrodinger equation in this case, but that only happens if $S = -Et$. Thus there is a fundamental

assumption involved i.e. $S(x,t) = -Et$ which is associated with $\exp(-iEt)$ from a bound state wavefunction.

We argue that this assumption is linked to the two flow/flux equations $d/dx \text{ partial } A = -$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E$. For the quantum case, one writes these as eigenvalue equations i.e. $id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ and $-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ with $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ as a solution. The momentum part of the full solution $-Et + px$ is 0. We argue that the flux/flow equations are key to the periodicity in quantum mechanics. One may start with flow/flux equations written as eigenvalue equations and find the solution for a free quantum particle $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. For a bound state, there is no overall momentum, but there is an average E so one would expect a factor of $\exp(-iEt)$. One may create a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and use this together with conservation of energy at x : $[\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m P(p/x)] + V(x) = E_n$ to also obtain the Schrodinger equation for a bound state where $E_n W$ is equivalent to $id/dt W(x,t)$ with $W(x) = \exp(-iEt)$. Thus one does not need the fluid equations to derive the Schrodinger equation.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Statistical Origin of Quantum Mechanics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0112049.pdf>